

A MATERIALS INFORMATICS APPROACH TOWARDS CREATING FUNCTIONALITY AT INTERFACES IN PMC

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1 Introduction

Interfaces constitute inherent disruptions of the phase character in polymer matrix composites, and due to the thermodynamic mismatch between adjoining components, lead to the formation of extended regions, or interphases, that accommodate the transition between contrasting materials characteristics. Resulting from complex chemical and physical processes during materials fabrication, these interphases often possess less than desirable properties, i.e., they may introduce mechanical weaknesses, thermal barriers, scattering centers, impurity repository, etc. Devising strategies for ameliorating the debilitating effects of interfaces requires a detailed understanding of the structural and chemical nature of interfacial regions. In this paper we describe a combined experimental and computational approach towards gaining the desired insight for carbon fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composites. Our approach, which consists of atomistic simulations, inelastic light scattering experiments, not only allows us to probe and elucidate interfacial structures and properties, but also to predictively explore new functionalities that can be inserted into these intermittent regions through appropriate molecular design.

2 Research Approach and Methodologies

2.1 Materials Preparation

The epoxy system used for this study was Epon 862 resin (diglycidylether of bisphenol) mixed with diethanolamine hardener. Resin and hardener were thoroughly stirred together at ratios ranging from under- to over-stoichiometric to map out possible conditions that may occur upon incomplete mixing (or de-mixing near interfaces), and curing was monitored at temperatures ranging from ambient to 50°C.

2.2 Inelastic Light Scattering

Materials characterization was done using *in-situ* concurrent micro-Raman (μ -RLS) and micro Brillouin light scattering (μ -BLS). While the former provides information about the changes in the system chemistry, from which we can derive the degree of cure, the latter allows us to measure the complex mechanical modulus at the nano-scale. Hence, besides yielding the visco-elastic properties of the curing polymer, BLS also yields structural information at the molecular scale by revealing the extent to which building blocks are mobile or connected to each other. The BLS signal arises from light scattered off propagating hypersonic waves, and as such, this technique allows one to associate a spatial orientation with the measured visco-elastic properties. For example, we can measure the elastic modulus perpendicular and parallel to interfaces, and based on observed anisotropy, draw conclusions about the adhesive properties between adjacent materials.

2.3 Atomistic Simulations

Our simulation framework includes (i) first-principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations to develop a detailed description of the interactions and chemical bonding across interfaces, in particular between dissimilar materials; (ii) large-scale molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, based on our reactive force field, to gain realistic atomistic representations of the polymer/nano-particle interfaces and to compute the mechanical, thermal, dielectric, and transport properties of the composites; and (iii) a hybrid MD/Monte Carlo (MC) technique, designed to accelerate the polymerization reactions and structural relaxation so as to generate realistic configurations of the simulated materials [1]. Because the time scales accessible by conventional MD simulations fall far short of encompassing reaction events

that lead to the formation of a polymer network, in our scheme, reactions are accelerated by inserting MC procedures in between MD simulation of the relaxation process. The formation of network bonds is based on the spatial proximity of reacting species. If the system experiences a net decrease in total potential energy, the new bond is kept, or otherwise rejected according to the Metropolis algorithm. Using this approach we have generated the structures of dicyclopentadiene (DCPD), which polymerizes based on a ruthenium-catalyzed ring-opening metathesis reaction, and successfully predicted its mechanical properties as a function of the degree of cure [2].

Fig.1. Elastic properties of epoxy as a function of the distance from the carbon fiber interface. Inset: map of Raman shifts revealing residual stresses in the epoxy matrix (red areas; carbon fiber cross sections are dark blue).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Interphase Formation

Systematic concurrent BLS/RLS characterization of epoxy during cure, with and without containing reinforcing carbon fibers revealed the following insights: The relationship between the degree of cure and the elastic properties of epoxy strongly depends on the temperature and the chemical composition of the resin-hardener system. This can lead to complicated spatial variations in the structural evolution, as exemplified in Fig. 1. The data show that the elastic

moduli are significantly lower near the interface than away from it, reflecting differing network topologies. The map of Raman peak shifts (inset of Fig. 2), however, reveals that chemical differences are much less pronounced, and are significant only in select areas (yellow patches). Hence, spatial variations in chemistry and mechanical properties do not overlay trivially.

3.2 Controlling Interphase Properties

From experiments we know that the network topology can be different in interphases than in the polymer bulk, without a corresponding disparity in the system chemistry. Our simulations reveal that polymers tend to develop a strongly layered structure and to densify near interfaces, which explains the experimental observations. Based on these findings, we seek to amplify or mitigate these developments by inserting various types of polymers in the interfacial region. Our approach is to explore the ability to tailor interfacial properties using predictive simulations and determine the theoretically possible magnitudes of the desired effects before attempting fabrication of such materials systems in the laboratory (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Model of multilayer structure to explore the ability for tailoring composite properties via predictive simulations.

References

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